

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: CANADA

Thermokarst lakes of the western Canadian Arctic

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Photo by Joshua Thienpont

Fig. 1 Lake- and pond-rich landscape of the Tuktoyaktuk Coastal Plains, western Canadian Arctic.

The greatest number of lakes and ponds on Earth are found in high-latitude regions of the northern hemisphere (Verpoorter *et al.*, 2014). Numerical assessments do not demonstrate the amazing diversity in form and function of Arctic waterbodies (Fig. 1). As would be expected for such a broad geographic extent, considerable diversity exists in the origins and ecosystem function of lakes across the circumpolar north. Understanding this diversity is essential both as we work to better characterize the aquatic

ecosystems on our planet and consider how they have been and continue to be affected by environmental changes.

A critical factor influencing both the prevalence of lakes and ponds in northern landscapes, as well as the way in which they manifest and function, is the presence, extent, and nature of permafrost. Defined as ground that remains frozen for two or more consecutive years, the make-up of permafrost and where it occurs is incredibly important for local and regional limnology. The proportion of the ground underlain by permafrost is used to delineate small-scale zones of permafrost extent. While the exact terminology and proportion can vary slightly by schema, most classify spatial coverage >90% as the continuous permafrost zone, the extensive discontinuous zone as 50-90% coverage, the isolated discontinuous zone as 10-50%, and sporadic coverage as <10% (Heginbottom *et al.*, 1995). Globally, lake area is decreasing in permafrost regions, though with regional heterogeneity (Nitzte *et al.*, 2018). However, permafrost extent is not the only factor that contributes to the impact on lake ecosystems. In many ways the make-up of the permafrost, particularly the amount of ice present, plays the dominant role. In areas of ice-rich permafrost the melting of excess ice can lead to a range of geomorphic disturbances and changes associated with ground subsidence, collectively referred to as thermokarst processes.

Thermokarst processes and lake and pond ecosystems are closely tied to one another. In areas of low relief, permafrost thaw leads to the formation of thermokarst lakes and ponds (Bouchard *et al.*, 2016). These aquatic ecosystems play an important role in the limnological and biogeochemical context of Arctic and subarctic environments (Olefeldt *et al.*, 2016). When thermokarst occurs in sloped terrain with higher relief, it can result in mass movement (*i.e.*, landslide) events and features, many of which occur around and on the shorelines of northern lakes, rivers, and coastal locations (Fig. 2). Arguably the most spectacular, and best studied of these thermokarst mass wasting features are shoreline retrogressive thaw slumps (Fig. 2B).

The western Canadian Arctic is a water-rich landscape that includes the low-lying Mackenzie Delta and surrounding upland terrain. This includes the Tuktoyaktuk Coastal Plains to the east, and west into the foothills of the Richardson Mountains. Banks Island, located further north in the Arctic Ocean, is also lake rich. The landscape east of the Richardson Mountains was glaciated during the last glacial period, and deglaciated relatively early compared to other northern regions in Canada. West of the Richardson Mountains, including the Old Crow Flats in the northern Yukon Territory, remained unglaciated. Given this history of glaciation and the resulting terrain, the permafrost across much of the western Canadian Arctic is rich in ground ice, and thus thermokarst features are very common.

Retrogressive thaw slumps are common disturbances on lake shorelines in ice-rich morainal terrain of the western Canadian Arctic (Kokelj *et al.*, 2023). The impacts of retrogressive thaw slumps on downstream lakes in the Tuktoyaktuk Coastal Plains has been well studied from both a contemporary limnology perspective, and over longer timescales using paleolimnological

Photos by Joshua Thienpont

Fig. 2 Hillslope thermokarst features impacting lakes in the western Canadian Arctic. A – translational slides in the Caribou Hills impacting a low-lying lake, B – a large (~220 m across) retrogressive thaw slump (*i.e.*, rotational slide) on the shore of a lake in the Tuktoyaktuk Coastal Plains.

methods. This work was initiated by my good friend and colleague Dr. Steve Kokelj (Northwest Territories Geological Survey) in the early 2000s. He established a series of paired lakes in the Mackenzie Delta uplands region, with the presence of a retrogressive thaw slump as the main distinguishing feature between paired lakes. From this dataset, lakes with thaw slump activity on their shorelines have been shown to have higher specific conductivity (and major ion concentrations), lower dissolved organic carbon and colour, and higher pH (Kokelj *et al.*, 2005) (Fig. 3). Further studies have shown that lakes with thaw slumps have lower total phosphorus and total dissolved nitrogen (Thompson *et al.*, 2012). Lakes with thaw slumps have

Fig. 3 Water samples from two nearby, paired lakes showing differences in water colour / DOC with thaw slump presence. The lake with no slump (7A) is highly stained, while the lake with a slump (7B) is relatively clear.

higher abundances of aquatic macrophytes because of increased water clarity (Mesquita *et al.*, 2010), corresponding to higher macroinvertebrate abundances (Moquin *et al.*, 2014) compared to lakes lacking thaw slumps. Using paleolimnological techniques, my past work has shown that sedimentary diatom assemblages in lakes with thaw slumps exhibited an increase in periphytic diatom diversity associated with slump activity, likely associated with greater habitat availability in a lake environment with increased

light availability and habitat substrate on macrophytes (Thienpont *et al.*, 2013). However, despite the consistent trends when comparing lakes with and without slumps, the degree of change across lakes at the onset of thaw slump initiation is quite wide. Much of my recent work has been focused on understanding the wide range of factors that influence how different lakes respond to slumping over broad spatial and temporal timescales.

One of the important, interesting, but also confounding factors associated with studying thaw slumps and their impacts on limnology is the role that the age and activity level of the slump itself plays. Retrogressive thaw slumps are “polycyclic”, alternating through phases of active slumping and stability over time. When a new slump forms on the shoreline of a lake, it persists as an actively growing slump for some time (years to decades) but eventually sediments and soils cover exposed ground ice, decreasing melt rates, and ultimately decreasing the slump’s ground ice ablation and overall thaw activity. This permits regrowth of vegetation, and the slump enters a period of stability. Lakes across the landscape exist in a range of states of lake stability, from highly active to stable for many decades (Fig. 4). On many lakes, slumps will re-activate and enter a renewed phase of growth, continuing cycles of polycyclic slumping that can occur an unknown number of times over long timescales. We have seen from the paired-lake comparisons mentioned above that it appears subsequent, polycyclic slumping events result in more muted limnological changes; in most lakes, the most significant changes occur when a new slump occurs. However, in some cases the renewed slumping is highly active and results in significant limnological change (Fig. 5). The western Canadian Arctic landscape contains a mosaic of aquatic ecosystems impacted by thaw slump disturbances of varying ages, sizes, and activity levels. The historical impacts of these factors contribute to the limnological conditions in the impacted lake ecosystems and have important implications for future change as warming continues to intensify.

Our current research is focused on the role landscape history plays on thaw slump activity and the repercussions for limnology. We are interested in understanding whether lakes with a prior history of thaw slump impacts may be insulated from future changes when slumps re-activate. In this way, we are working to discover how and to what extent past slumping results in an ecological memory of previous disturbance in lake ecosystems, muting further impacts when slumps re-activate. We have also identified several cases where re-activated slumps appear to be

Fig. 4 Lakes in the Tuktoyaktuk Coastal Plains impacted by thaw slumps of varying ages and activity levels. A, B - highly active thaw slumps compared to C, D - slumps that are re-vegetated and stabilized.

Fig. 5 Change of a thaw slump over time on the shoreline of a single lake. This lake had a previous slump on its shoreline, but this highly active slump that re-initiated in the early 2000s dramatically changed the lake ecosystem. A - highly active thaw slump in 2008, B - the same thaw slump in the winter of 2010, and C - the same slump exhibiting significant growth and vegetation development in the summer of 2023, likely beginning to enter a period of stability.

resulting in highly enhanced impacts in several lakes (Fig. 5). It is important to understand what is driving this intensification, and if these enhanced, re-activated slumps are more likely to occur as the region rapidly warms. Ultimately, we are interested in how lakes are going to change in the future, and whether an understanding of landscape legacies can help us predict future limnological changes across the western Arctic.

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